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A STUDY ON THE ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT IN VISAKHAPATNAM DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Entrepreneurship contributes to economic development in several ways viz., assembling various factors of production, bearing the risks, innovating and initiating the techniques of production to reduce the cost and increase its quality and quantity, expanding the horizons the market, and coordinating and managing the manufacturing unit at various levels. Entrepreneurs are thus seeds of industrial development and fruits of industrial development of a country crucially depends upon the number of and abilities entrepreneurs and not merely on the availability of resources. The study is empirical one. The main objective of this study is to analyze the identify influencing successful factors for entrepreneurial development and finally give suggestions for promoting entrepreneurial development . For collecting data personal interviews and field surveys are conducted. Both primary and secondary source of data were used in this study. To collect the necessary data, an interview schedule was drawn up. Simple statistical tools such as averages and percentages were used to quantify the data.

Key words: Entrepreneurship, industrial development, interview schedule

The term entrepreneur is derived from the French word entrepreneur denoting to undertake. In the early 16th century it was applied to persons engaged to military expeditions and extends to cover construction and civil engineering activities in the 17th century but during the 18th century the word entrepreneur differently. It means an individual providing the fourth factor of production namely enterprise. According to Timmons (1986) "Entrepreneurship is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing". Fundamentally it is a human creative act, it is the knack of sensing an opportunity where others see Chaos, contradictions and confusion. Above all an entrepreneur is one who creates incline to innovation that is finding new things or doing things that are already being done in a new way.

Entrepreneurship contributes to economic development in several ways viz., assembling various factors of production, bearing the risks, innovating and initiating the techniques of production to reduce the cost and increase its quality and quantity, expanding the horizons the market, and coordinating and managing the manufacturing unit at various levels. Entrepreneurs are thus seeds of industrial development and fruits of industrial development of a country crucially depends upon the number of factors and abilities of entrepreneurs and not merely on the availability of resources. More employment opportunities to unemployed youth, increase per capita income, higher standard of living and increased the savings of individual, revenue to the government in the form of income tax, sales tax, export duties, import duties, and balanced regional development.

Significance of the study:

Visakhapatnam, one of the oldest towns in Andhra Pradesh, is situated between Madras and Calcutta on the East-Coast along the sea shore of Bay of Bengal in a picturesque amphitheatre of hills. This costal district in the North east of Andhra Pradesh borders. The stage of Orissa on the North and Vizianagaram on the North-East, to its south is East Godavari. Its eastern shore on the Bay of Bengal is one hundred and sixth kilometers long and the entire coast is sandy with salt swamps. Visakhapatnam city, popularly called the City of destiny" has been witnessing phenomenal growth in terms of industrial development and infrastructure facilities. Visakhapatnam the rising steel city, throbbing with anaritime activity is fast developing into one of the premier industrial centers in the world.

Besides, the first even port based steel plant, it also houses same of the major public and privatge4 sector units, viz..... Hindustan shipyard, Bharat Heavy Plate and Vessels limited, Hindustan Zinc limited, Hindustan polymers, coromandal Fertilizers Corporation limited

Among the various cities in Andhra Pradesh, Visakhapatnam has registered an impressive growth of small – scale units in recent years due to the presence of large number of large sized public and private sector undertaking.

Objectives:

- To study the socio-economic backgrounds of entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam district
- To analyze the identify influencing successful factors for entrepreneurial development
- To give suggestions for promoting entrepreneurial development.

Methodology:

The study is empirical one. For collecting data personal interviews and field surveys are conducted. Both primary and secondary source of data were used in this study. Primary data was collected from the entrepreneurs and for the secondary data, related books and pamphlets were referred.

Tools used:

To collect the necessary data, an interview schedule was drawn up. Simple statistical tools such as averages and percentages were used to quantify the data.

Sampling:

A simple random sample of 90 entrepreneurs was selected from Visakhapatnam district for this study.

Findings:

- Out of 90 entrepreneurs selected for this study. It was found that the mean age of entrepreneurs was 40 and the maximum number of entrepreneurs was in the age group of 35-45 years.
- Almost all the entrepreneurs are male. As revealed by the survey, women entrepreneurs are very insignificant.
- All the entrepreneurs were registered with the District Industries Centre, Visakhapatnam.
- About 55 percent are entrepreneurs based on manufacturing units. 30 per cent run bricks, stone crushers, and 15 per cent are involved in other businesses.
- About 32 per cent of the entrepreneurs were from mercantile communities and 68 per cent of the entrepreneurs were from non-traditional business communities. They were forced entrepreneurs. It is contrary to the popular belief that entrepreneurs are drawn mostly from merchant classes. This is an encouraging trend.

Regarding the survey, the entrepreneurs encounter several problems. 35 percent of the entrepreneurs experienced problems related to raw materials, 42 per cent of the respondents felt the lack of finance, 18 per cent of the respondents faced marketing problems, and 5 percent faced transport problems

Suggestions: The following are the suggestions for the promotion of entrepreneurial development

- Demand based pollution free industries should be started on a large scale basis. This will serve the needs of the people and provide employment opportunities to a large number of educated youth in Visakhapatnam district.
- Separate financial institutions like Small Business Finance Corporation, SHGs should be set up exclusively for meeting the financial requirements of small scale industries.
- Reservations of a few items of products exclusively for manufacturing in small scale industries of Visakhapatnam should be made. This will promote industrial development in these areas.
- Loan amount should be increased in order to purchase raw material and equipments.
- The young minds should be identified and encouraged to start industries in these areas. This would solve the unemployment problems to some extent.

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